

NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN IS 105 YEARS OLD**Shakhnoza Sobirova Nasimovna**

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Abstract: In this article talks about the establishment, development and current attention of the National University of Uzbekistan in Central Asia.

Key words: medicine, physics-mathematics, social-economics, technical history-philology, labor organic and colloid chemistry.

INTRODUCTION

The foundation stone of the National University of Uzbekistan was laid on April 9, 1918. On this day, the organizational board of the Turkestan Muslim People's Darulfunun was formed, 9 meetings were held for a month, and on May 3, 1918, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov was elected as the chairman (rector). May 12, 1918, when the Turkistan Muslim People's University was officially opened, became a historical date for the foundation of a new modern education system. In a short period of time, 299 teachers were recruited to the faculties of natural-mathematics, agriculture, technology, social economy, literature and philosophy of the university. Among them were dozens of well-known poets and writers, authors of textbooks written for Jadid schools, as well as leading representatives of about 20 different fields of science. For example, Fitrat taught mother tongue, Abdulla Avloni taught literature, Munavvarqori taught ethics, Kamal Shamsi taught mathematics, and Burhan Habib taught political history.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

On May 31, 1918, the university publication "Halk Darulfununi" newspaper began to be published. In the same year, Turkestan People's Library, Turkestan

People's Museum, Conservatory, Oriental Institute were formed within the university. By the decision of the government of Turkestan in December 1919, Turkestan Muslim People's Darulfunu was granted the status of Turkestan State University (TSU) and entered a new stage of development. Since 1920, six faculties (medicine, physics-mathematics, social-economics, technical history-philology and labor) have been operating at Turkestan State University. The number of university students reached 2671, among them there were representatives of 24 nationalities.

On February 19, 1920, an echelon loaded with dozens of leading professors, their families, and equipment necessary for the educational process left Moscow for Tashkent. In 1921, for the first time in the history of the university, 12 specialists in the field of medicine were trained. In 1923, four more faculties - agriculture, reclamation engineering, local economy and law faculties were established. This year, 79 people graduated from the university: 25 doctors, 14 agronomists, 8 engineers and 32 lawyers. Many of them later became known as great scientists and specialists in the world of science. In connection with the establishment of the Faculty of Pedagogy, the Institute of Public Education named after Timiryazev under the People's Commissariat of Education of the Republic was included in the university. On July 17, 1923, Turkestan State University was granted the status of State University of Central Asia. From November 1923, the "News of the Central Asian State University" ("Bulleten Sredne-Aziatskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta") began to be published. This publication, which publishes scientific research on various topics, soon came to the attention of world scientists. In 1925, "Central Asian State University" was published. This is evidenced by the fact that "Darulfununi News" was sent to 278 foreign universities and 438 higher schools and research centers in 1929.

In order to further increase the scientific potential of university students, to inform them about the latest developments in the world of science, the university library has been enriched with new textbooks every year. In 1924, the number of books in the university library fund reached 75,000 copies. Most of them consisted of rare

manuscripts. By 1940, the library had a collection of 376,000 books. In 1928, B. P. Grabovsky, a researcher at the Faculty of Physics, created the world's first television transmission device ("telephoto"). In 1971, this discovery was confirmed by UNESCO, and Uzbekistan was recognized as the homeland of television. During the years 1939-1940, specialists in such fields as mathematics, mechanics, soil science, geography, physics, geophysics, botany, zoology, anthropology, history, organic and colloid chemistry, analytical chemistry, winemaking, oil technology were trained at the university. prepared.

RESULTS

The Second World War was a special testing year for our country. From the first days of the war, a number of university scientists and students went to fight as volunteers. Educational and scientific activities at the university were reorganized according to the requirements of the war years. First of all, attention was paid to the areas important for the country's defense. The five-year educational system was changed to three years, taking into account the military situation, and the curriculum and textbooks were redesigned accordingly. In November 1943, in connection with the establishment of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, university scientists T.A. Sarimsakov, V.I. Romanovsky, A.S. Uklonsky and other professors were elected full members of UzRFA, professors E.P. Korovin and I.P. Sukervanik were elected as corresponding members.

In 1960, the name of Central Asian State University was changed to Tashkent State University. Tashkent State University, which became one of the most prestigious higher educational institutions in the 60s of the 20th century, became a center of science and education that trains personnel not only for Uzbekistan or Central Asia, but also for all developing countries of the East. In 1967, a student town was established, the faculties of Chemistry and Physics of the university were put into operation, and in 1970, 12-story administrative and 5-story main educational buildings were put into operation. Preparatory faculty for more than a thousand students from more than 20

countries of Asia, Africa and Latin America has started work. The university has developed scientific directions in many fields of science. The activity of the existing scientific schools has been further expanded. Since 1967, TashDU has become one of the 25 leading higher educational institutions in the former union.

On September 14, 1995, Tashkent State University was named after Mirzo Ulugbek, a great scientist and thinker of the East, taking into account his incomparable contribution to the development of the education system, his great achievements in personnel training, the wishes of the country's public and university scientists. By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2000, Tashkent State University was granted the status of a National University. The national status is strengthened by the presence of scientists among the graduates of the university who have raised the name of our country to the heights and are making a worthy contribution to the development of science. In particular, people's writers such as Oybek, Mukhtar Avezov, Asqad Mukhtar, Odil Yaqubov, Pirimkul Kadirov, Shukur Kholmirezayev, O'tkir Hashimov, who studied at the university, made a worthy contribution to the enrichment of the artistic treasure with their works.

CONCLUSION

Heroes of Uzbekistan such as Azod Sharafiddinov, Said Ahmed, Erkin Vahidov, Abdulla Oripov, Suyima Ganiyeva, Turgun Azlarov have grown up from the university. Yu.A. Izrael, a graduate of the Faculty of Physics and Mathematics of the University, in 1978-1990, the chairman of the State Committee on Hydrometeorology and Natural Environment Control of the former Union worked in the position. For his work in popularizing and strengthening knowledge about climate change and stopping the spread of negative processes. In 2007 Yu.A. Israel was awarded the Nobel Prize. R. Kasimjonov, a student of the National University, became the world champion, and S. Qayumov became the Asian champion in this type of chess. 8 of the 13 Presidents who worked at the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan are university graduates. 43 scientific schools created at the university now make an incomparable contribution to

the development of various fields of science. They are taking the activities of recognized scientific schools such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, geology, biology, and archeology to a new level. Today, UzMU has high-potential professors and teachers, modern material and technical base, and internationally recognized scientific schools, necessary for the development of the educational process and scientific-research areas.

The Faculty of Journalism of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek was first opened in 1949 as a department within the Faculty of Philology of the Central Asian State University. In 1967, the department of journalism gained the status of a faculty. Professor Tugan Ernazarov, Doctor of History, was appointed the first dean of the Faculty of Journalism.

In 1999, the first undergraduate graduates of the faculty, and in 2001, the first graduates of the faculty's master's specialty graduated. By 2001, a digital and analog TV and radio studio, a mini-typography, and an information resource center started working at the faculty.

About professors and teachers

The total number of professors and teachers is 58, including:

11 doctors of science

20 candidates of science

11 Ph.D

16 teachers without academic degrees

Number of educational programs:

Bachelor - 3 majors

Master's degree - 4 specialties

There is 1 specialized scientific council that grants scientific degrees (DSc, PhD).

IMPORTANT DATES IN THE HISTORY OF THE FACULTY:

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In 2004, professors and teachers of the faculty released 2 documentaries (40 minutes each) in Uzbek and English.

In 2004, the faculty got its own website.

In 2004, "Master-classes" were organized by mature local publicists and journalists at the faculty.

In 2005, higher journalism courses were opened at the faculty.

In 2012, the leading editorial offices of the Republic created "Schools of Skills" at the faculty in order to train qualified journalists.

In 2015, the Faculty of Journalism moved to a new campus.

In 2015, the "Young Journalists' Club" was established in cooperation with the Creative Union of Journalists of Uzbekistan.

In 2016, 2 associate professors of our faculty won the Republican competition "The best pedagogue of the year".

In 2017, 1 associate professor of our faculty won the Republican competition "The best pedagogue of the year".

In 2018, a new University of Journalism and Mass Communications was established.

In 2018, 2 teachers received the title of professor.

Currently, almost all graduate students and masters of the faculty are working in UzMTRK and regional branches, republican and regional editorial offices, press service departments of ministries and organizations.

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